

Emotional Expression: Implications for Dyadic Relationship Quality During Adolescence

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Adolescence is a critical period for personal development in addition to the development and maintenance of relationships; it provides a context where individuals can socialize in different environments (Harris, 1995). For adolescents, both interpersonal and intrapersonal relationship dynamics can pose challenges to development. This includes varying degrees of mental health issues, aggressiveness, peer pressure, peer stress, and antisocial behaviors (Rose & Rudolph, 2006; Piehler & Dishion, 2007). If damaging behaviors persist in adolescents, the individual may not experience constructive growth and may instead endure persisting inhibitory trends to personal development (Rose & Rudolph, 2006). With the rapidly increasing rate of interactions and stimuli in the modern age, anyone - regardless of background - could be affected by these same issues. In particular, adolescents expose themselves to a multitude of harmful factors as they engage in new, eclectic behaviors within most relationships (Smetana et al., 2006). Issues within relationships and barriers between adolescents may be resolved by certain constructs if research can identify problems that hinder and prescribe processes that aid individuals during this critical developmental period.

Adolescent Relationships

Adolescents are likely to participate in both peer groups and dyadic relationships, and both contexts have considerable effects on personal development (Laird et al., 1999). Connections between adolescents and parents, siblings, grandparents, peers, a romantic interest, or other relationships create unique conditions for character development during adolescence (Smetana et al., 2006). Quality, or the general measure of closeness (companionship, disclosure, emotional support, approval, satisfaction) and discord (conflict, criticism, pressure, exclusion, dominance) in relationships, is a reliable predictor of beneficial and adverse effects on

development (Furman & Buhrmester, 1985; Piehler & Dishion, 2007; Chow et al., 2012; Chow & Tan, 2013). Studies also imply better relationship quality correlates with more trust, attachment, and satisfaction, so further analysis of quality within adolescent relationships may reveal nuanced solutions to an array of issues.

Peer groups in adolescence tend to be between individuals of the same sex (Laird et al., 1999; Rose & Rudolph, 2006). When considering social-emotional issues, boys tend to engage in rougher, self-interested behaviors while girls tend to focus on relationship-oriented behaviors (Chu, 2005; Rose & Rudolph, 2006). This difference can be attributed to boys' masculine behaviors, including protecting vulnerabilities and proving masculinity, and girls' ruminative feminine behaviors (Chu, 2005). Although the masculine behaviors of boys disrupt certain beneficial factors of relationships like empathy and intimacy, boys employ alternate behaviors, like humor, which can also benefit relationships (Chu, 2005). This gender difference has intensified the pressures faced by males in the modern age; more interactions may engender more emotional affairs. For adolescent boys, this may imply additional developmental struggles due to a lack of beneficial relationship qualities.

However, more gender similarities can be found in dyadic relationships. In adolescents, dyadic relationships, or relationships consisting of two individuals regardless of sex, are found to have higher degrees of beneficial qualities than peer groups (Cillessen et al., 2005). This difference can be attributed to greater opportunities for intimacy between two individuals as opposed to a network of individuals; adolescents may feel more compelled to express themselves within a dyad, promoting the development of better relationships and character. Furthermore, individuals tend to engage in more deviant, or non-normative, behavior in dyads (Rose, 2002; Piehler & Dishion, 2007). For instance, revealing vulnerabilities would be considered deviant

behavior for boys. Non-normative behaviors may not be easily accepted by a peer group, ergo both boys and girls exhibit these behaviors more frequently in dyads. Closeness can be attributed to comfort and similarity in relationships, and individuals tend to form dyads with those who are similar to them; those who engage in antisocial or non-supportive behaviors feel more comfortable with each other (Laird et al., 1999). The focus of this study falls onto dyadic relationships as they are critical environments for adolescents.

Co-rumination

Adolescents more frequently consider personal problems and engage in certain behaviors to deal with those problems in the intimate environments fostered by dyadic relationships (Piehler & Dishion, 2007; Chow et al., 2012). One notable behavior and factor in adolescent development is co-rumination. Defined as the dwelling on and extensively discussing negative feelings with another individual, co-rumination is a recent conceptualization (Rose, 2021). It is commonly found in dyadic relationships due to increased intimacy and has differing social and emotional implications for adolescent males and females. Though co-rumination can address all types of problems, individuals tend to focus on interpersonal problems, like family affairs, rather than non-interpersonal problems, like academics. Co-rumination is most prominent in girls during late childhood through middle adolescence (Rose, 2021). Although it is generally agreed that talking about one's problems makes people feel better, pondering about issues for prolonged periods via co-rumination can have detrimental effects; the construct has various trade-offs. This bidirectional effect is pertinent as the social and emotional aspects of co-rumination can be independently analyzed.

Co-rumination has social benefits in regard to the discussion of problems. An individual may build trust and support as a result of the self-disclosure, defined as the disclosure of private

information like emotions, feelings, or problems to another individual (Rose, 2021). Generally, disclosing one's problems to another helps relieve stress and increase morale (Chow et al., 2012). This is because cathartic experiences and positive, supportive responses from listeners help individuals better understand and interpret feelings (Legerski et al., 2015). For self-disclosure within a dyad, the person who discloses is referred to as an 'actor' while the person who listens is referred to as a 'partner'. One can find gender differences in disclosure itself as well. Both genders report more positive experiences when disclosing to girls; girls tend to be more supportive and engaged during problem talk compared to boys (Borowski & Rose, 2021). These positive subjective experiences generate a better understanding and perception of problems and relationships. On the other hand, boys tend to joke about emotions to cope or avoid problem talk altogether to avoid the uncomfortable or weird feelings they may associate with vulnerability (Rose et al., 2012). Though the behaviors of girls may seem more productive, individuals find benefits from different habits. If individuals employ a moderation of these gender-linked behaviors, they may fare better than those who only employ one style of relationship processes (Rose & Rudolph, 2006). In essence, self-disclosure has beneficial implications for individuals which can be achieved through various means.

Emotionally, co-rumination has harmful outcomes. A major aspect of the construct is contemplating problems, so individuals may end up dwelling on these hazardous feelings. This causes internalization of pernicious feelings, and can later result in depressive symptoms (Rose, 2021). Inherently, these dangerous tendencies take a toll on personal development. Although problems can be an avenue for bonding in adolescents, problems should be addressed and dealt with in manners which promote constructive development. This notion stimulates investigation into methods in which individuals can favorably address interpersonal issues.

Hypothesis

Overall, co-rumination is a driving factor of character development in the dyadic relationships of adolescents. This study seeks to draw a correlation between relationship quality, a predictor of advantageous developmental outcomes in adolescents, in regard to the intensity of self-disclosure, the positive facet of co-rumination. In other words, what is the association between the intensity of self-disclosure and dyadic relationship quality during adolescence? I hypothesize that relationship quality will increase with a greater intensity of self-disclosure. In general, people who self-disclose will have higher quality dyadic relationships than those who do not self-disclose. This would mean adolescents who engage in self-disclosure would end up with more beneficial traits than those who do not engage in self-disclosure.

Research Gap

This study will address a gap in current research pertaining to co-rumination and explore a discontinuity in research on adolescent development through a questionnaire. As a new construct, co-rumination has limited research, and its contributing factors have changed rapidly over time. This means a study on correlations between constructs would provide more nuanced knowledge on adolescent relationship tendencies. Depending on the findings of this study, adolescents would primarily benefit from this study; knowledge of behaviors in adolescence relationships with positive implications may help improve relationships. Indirect audiences include researchers, educators, and other mental health-related professionals who may benefit from new information regarding constructs relating to mental health and adolescence.

Method

Study Design

This study was conducted with a quantitative approach. This study aimed to explore the correlation between two variables: the intensity of self-disclosure and dyadic relationship quality during adolescence. Participants' behaviors were assessed via Likert scale which measured the frequency of certain behaviors using closed-ended, rated items. Numerous studies regarding topics related to self-disclosure and relationship quality employed quantitative measures. Characteristics of constructs such as self-disclosure and relationships were examined with scales that measured the frequency at which a behavior occurred (Laird et al., 1999; Rose, 2002; Calmes & Roberts, 2008).

This study employed a correlational research design. Because the study approach was quantitative, the measured extent of both variables was analyzed. To answer the research question, the analysis focused on the comparison of variable trends: direct and inverse relationships between self-disclosure intensity and relationship quality. This design helped reach an adequate sample size while preserving a consistent standard that would facilitate comparison. Previous studies have investigated correlations between numerous similar constructs relating to co-rumination such as empathy, intimacy, and conflict (Cillessen et al., 2005; Chow et al., 2013).

This study was limited by response bias, nuanced assumptions, and population. A proclivity of respondents was to answer questions quickly without much thought. Furthermore, participants may have responded to items with biased positive self-concepts. The study assumed that participants engaged in at least one dyadic relationship and discussed emotional topics with another individual. Finally, the study examined only a small sample of the population that may not necessarily reflect the true nature of the target population.

Participants

Participants were adolescents aged 15 to 19 in the 11th or 12th grades at Viera High School. The sample was composed of individuals from middle and upper-middle class families. This study used non-probability convenience sampling to feasibly collect data. A Google Form questionnaire was distributed via email to multiple upperclassmen AP teachers at school. These teachers were requested to post the Form on Google Classroom for students to fill out.

Ethical risks were minimal for this study. Identities of participants were kept anonymous, and the questionnaire was not very intrusive; it asked general questions about personal social-emotional habits in a relationship. The only anticipated risk was feeling triggered by questions mentioning negative personal experiences.

Materials

This study required internet access and an electronic communication device to complete the questionnaire, which was created and administered via Google Forms for feasibility. Two validated instruments - the Emotional Self-Disclosure Scale (ESDS) and the Network of Relationships Inventory-Relationship Qualities Version (NRI-RQV) - were adapted into a single questionnaire that was used in the study. The validity of this instrument was ensured by maintaining consistency with key elements of the adapted instruments. Additionally, questions were arranged randomly and data was analyzed with methods similar to those in studies that employed these instruments.

Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed to six Viera High School teachers who then invited students in their AP classes to participate by posting the questionnaire to their Google Classroom streams. Participants completed the questionnaire online on their own time. Participants were

asked to answer questions in regard to a partner in a dyad and responded to prompts such as “How often have you discussed times when you felt depressed?” and “How often do you spend fun time with this person?”. Questionnaires were administered for four weeks.

Measures

This study employed a questionnaire consisting of three sections. The first section included four demographic items relating to grade level, gender, and relationship type. The second section included 16 items relating to self-disclosure, and the third section included 20 items relating to dyadic relationship quality. The second and third sections were truncated versions of separate instruments. A copy of the questionnaire is presented in Appendix C.

Self-Disclosure

The 40-item Emotional Self-Disclosure Scale (ESDS) was adapted for this research and assesses the extent, or intensity, to which participants engage in self-disclosure with a counselor figure to discuss instances of certain emotions (Snell et al., 1988). Eight content areas, or subscales, are assessed: (1) depression, (2) happiness, (3) jealousy, (4) anxiety, (5) anger, (6) calmness, (7) apathy, and (8) fear. Each subscale was assessed by five items each. Items were designed with consideration for the frequency of the behavior rather than the nature of the behavior. Wording remained consistent between items, differing only for the specific emotion. For example, items for the depression content area include “Times when you felt depressed” and “Times when you felt discouraged”. An example item for each content area is presented in Appendix A. Participants rated each item on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (0) “I have not discussed this topic with my counselor” to (4) “I have fully discussed this topic with my counselor” in terms of the degree to which the item described self-disclosure propensities. Content areas were analyzed using the rating of each item for the subscale. This study’s

instrument employs a truncated version of the ESDS for the purposes of this research. Though each content area was preserved, five items per subscale were reduced to two items per subscale. Though the wording of each item was slightly altered, the intent was kept consistent. For example, “Times when you felt depressed” was altered to “How often have you discussed times when you felt depressed?”. Furthermore, the 5-point Likert scale was altered to range from (1) “Never or hardly at all” to (5) “Always or extremely much”. Alterations occurred to better match the nature of this study.

Dyadic Relationship Quality

The 30-item Network of Relationships Inventory-Relationship Qualities Version (NRI-RQV) was also adapted for this research and assesses the supportive and discordant characteristics of the participants’ relationships (Furman & Buhrmester, 1985). Ten subscales are assessed: (1) companionship, (2) intimate disclosure, (3) pressure, (4) satisfaction, (5) conflict, (6) emotional support, (7) criticism, (8) approval, (9) dominance, and (10) exclusion. Each subscale was assessed by three items each. Items were designed with consideration for the frequency of the characteristic behavior rather than the nature of the characteristic behavior. Wording remained consistent for most items, differing for only the specific behavior. For example, items for the companionship subscale include “How often do you spend fun time with this person?” and “How often do you and this person go places and do things together?”. An example item for each subscale is presented in Appendix B. Participants rated each item on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from (1) “Never or hardly at all” to (5) “Always or extremely much” in terms of the degree to which the item described characteristic behavior propensities within the relationship. Content areas were analyzed by averaging the three items that made up each subscale. Furthermore, two additional quality factors can be derived from the subscales:

closeness and discord. Closeness scores were the mean score of the companionship, disclosure, emotional support, approval, and satisfaction scales, while discord scores were the mean score of the conflict, criticism, pressure, exclusion, and dominance scales. This study's instrument employs a truncated version of the NRI-RQV for the purposes of this research. Though each content area was preserved, three items per subscale were reduced to two items per subscale. Wording for most items was kept consistent.

Data Analysis

Data from each section was organized independently. Analysis of both data sets was completed by scoring respective subscales, computing correlation coefficients, deriving means and standard deviations, and comparing these values. For the ESDS section, an "intensity" scale score was derived from the quantity of content areas that had a high score and the rating of the respective content areas with high scores. This "intensity" score was compared against the closeness and discord factor scores from the NRI-RQV section; correlational analysis was performed on the intensity, closeness, and discord scores to find trends between constructs in responses. After, further separate analyses were conducted using the primary results. In each response, trends in the primary self-disclosure-relationship quality results were compared with the participant's gender and relationship type for additional insight.

Results

The research instrument was distributed to six teachers at Viera High School. All 61 students who responded to the form were upperclassmen and were enrolled in at least one AP course. Of the respondents, 33 (54%) were in the 11th grade and 28 (46%) were in the 12th grade. Twenty-nine (48%) of the respondents were female, 31 (51%) were male, and 1 (1%) respondent self-identified as non-binary. Of the dyad partners, 32 (53%) were identified as female and 29 (47%) were identified as male. Data regarding grade level was not collected for dyad partners. Of the reported dyadic relationship types, 46 (75%) were friends, 13 (21%) were romantic partners, one (2%) was a classmate, and one (2%) was a sibling. For the purposes of this study, classmate and sibling relationships were grouped into one category for analysis. One respondent answered “friend AND classmate” to the question regarding dyadic relationship type, and it was decided to code this response as a friend.

No other demographics were collected. However, the sample was drawn from the Viera High School student body. This population of 2298 students was 48% female and 52% male; however, there were a small number of students who did not identify as either female or male. The population was 5% African American, 4% Asian, 15% Hispanic, 68% Caucasian, less than 1% American Indian, less than 1% Pacific Islander, and 7% multi-racial.

This study relied on self-reported data. Items consisted of Likert scales to quantify data. This produces a limitation for the study; data may not be completely representative of the population because participants might not have responded with complete honesty. Participants might have been biased and skewed responses towards the aim of the study.

This study combined two instruments which were truncated to reduce research fatigue. The Emotional Self-Disclosure Scale (ESDS), designed by Snell et al., 1988, was employed for

the self-disclosure aspect of the study, and the Network of Relationships Inventory-Relationship Qualities Version (NRI-RQV), by Furman and Buhrmester, 1985, was employed for the relationship quality aspect of the study. Both instruments used Likert scales and, for the purposes of this study, some questions were adapted to allow a consistent item scale (1 = Never or hardly at all, 2 = Seldom or not too much, 3 = Sometimes or somewhat, 4 = Often or very much, and 5 = Always or extremely much) for the entire questionnaire. A copy of the questionnaire and model items can be found in the Appendices.

Self-disclosure intensity was measured by the eight aforementioned subscales with two items each (depression, anxiety, calmness, apathy, fear, happiness, jealousy, and anger). Intensity scores for each respondent were derived by crossing the number of subscales scored 7 or greater and the average subscale score for any score greater than 7. Means (*M*) and standard deviations (*SD*) were calculated for each subscale, as shown in Table 1.

Intensity score means were calculated for the entire sample and each gender “pathway”. Pathways included female-to-female (FF), male-to-male (MM), male-to-female (MF), and female-to-male (FM). Because existing research has not touched upon genders other than female and male, the data from the respondent who self-identified as non-binary was excluded from all gender-related analyses.

Table 1

Emotional Self-Disclosure Scale Subscale Means and Standard Deviations

	Depression	Anxiety	Calmness	Apathy	Fear	Happiness	Jealousy	Anger
<i>M</i>	5.36	6.28	6.49	4.80	5.33	7.38	5.00	6.80
<i>SD</i>	2.12	2.31	2.38	2.02	2.10	2.18	2.28	2.44

Note. $n = 61$.

Next, intensity score means were calculated for each relationship type. This study provided options including friend or best friend (FRI), romantic partner (RP), classmate, sibling, counselor, and other. The classmate, sibling, counselor, and other options were combined into one category (CSO) because responses were sparse. Additionally, intensity score means were calculated for each gender-relationship. This consisted of the gender pathway and relationship type. Female-to-male friends (FMFRI), female-to-male romantic partners (FMRP), and so on were coded by combining gender and relationship codes. Same-sex romantic partners and all gender CSO categories were not computed due to lack of responses. Finally, to find any differences between same-sex and cross-sex relationship behaviors, intensity score means were calculated after combining MF and FM categories into a cross-gender category (CG) for self-disclosure intensity and friendships (CG, CGFRI). A CGRP category was not included because there were no same-sex RP results to compare against. Intensity score means for each discussed gender, relationship, and gender-relationship category are presented in Table 2.

Table 2

Intensity Means for Sample, Gender, Relationship, and Gender-Relationship Categories

Relationship	FRI	RP	CSO
	3.12	4.10	2.80
Sample	3.36		
Gender			
FF	3.30	3.36	
MM	2.67	2.53	
MF	3.23	3.65	3.11
FM	5.30	5.15	5.36
CG	4.14	4.40	

Note. $n = 61$.

These point-scores show that females reported greater intensity of self-disclosure than males; the FF and FM categories scored higher than the MM and MF categories. On average, cross-gender dyads also reported greater intensity of self-disclosure than same-sex categories; the CG category scored higher than both the FF and MM categories. Finally, romantic partners reported greater intensity of self-disclosure than other types of relationships; the RP category scored higher than both the FRI and CSO categories.

Dyadic relationship quality was measured with two scales: closeness and discord. Closeness, or beneficial relationship quality from constructive behaviors, was composed of five subscales with two items each: companionship, support, disclosure, satisfaction, and approval. Discord, or adverse relationship quality from damaging behaviors, was also composed of five subscales with two items each: dominance, exclusion, pressure, conflict, and criticism. Means and standard deviations were calculated for each subscale and are shown in Table 3. Closeness and discord score means were calculated for the same categories as self-disclosure intensity and are presented in Tables 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 3

Network of Relationships Inventory-Relationship Qualities Version Subscale Means and Standard Deviations

	Companionship	Support	Disclosure	Satisfaction	Approval
<i>M</i>	4.07	3.46	3.55	4.41	3.93
<i>SD</i>	0.94	1.13	1.24	0.68	0.79
	Dominance	Exclusion	Pressure	Conflict	Criticism
<i>M</i>	2.60	1.69	1.75	1.49	1.88
<i>SD</i>	0.83	0.75	0.76	0.71	0.96

Note. $n = 61$.

Table 4*Closeness Means for Sample, Gender, Relationship, and Gender-Relationship Categories*

Relationship		FRI	RP	CSO
		3.70	4.48	4.05
Sample	3.88			
Gender				
FF	3.96	3.95		
MM	3.50	3.45		
MF	4.15	3.60	4.39	
FM	4.43	4.05	4.58	
CG	4.26	3.78		

Note. n = 61.

The closeness scores reflect the same conclusions as the previously discussed intensity scores. The discord scores are all less than 2.00; overall, there are less adverse qualities than beneficial qualities in relationships, meaning most adolescents have good quality relationships.

Table 5*Discord Means for Sample, Gender, Relationship, and Gender-Relationship Categories*

Relationship		FRI	RP	CSO
		1.87	1.93	1.80
Sample	1.88			
Gender				
FF	1.84	1.84		
MM	1.91	1.92		
MF	1.84	1.77	1.87	
FM	1.99	1.85	2.04	
CG	1.90	1.80		

Note. n = 61.

This study sought to find a correlation between self-disclosure intensity and dyadic relationship quality. Intensity was compared with closeness and discord scores (IC, ID) using the Pearson correlation coefficient. Self-disclosure intensity and beneficial dyadic relationship quality were significantly and moderately positively correlated ($r = .61$) as shown in Figure 1. Because self-disclosure intensity and beneficial relationship quality are positively correlated, it can be assumed that those who disclose more tend to be in higher-quality relationships. Self-disclosure and relationship quality may be accurate predictors of each other. Because many implications are connected and run to and from each construct, a wide array of benefits are possible. Furthermore, adolescents may benefit from disclosure because it may foster better relationships and help reduce the drawback of social-emotional issues.

Figure 1

Self-Disclosure Intensity vs. Closeness

Note. $n = 52$.

$p < .007$

Conversely, self-disclosure intensity and adverse relationship quality were shown to have little to no correlation in this study ($r = .03$). Although a negative correlation would be desired since greater self-disclosure intensities would drive adverse relationship qualities down, the absence of a correlation means self-disclosure may not have as much to do with poor relationship quality. If an individual does not self-disclose as much or as deeply, or only dwells on damaging subjects, they can still have good quality relationships.

Co-variants

Further correlations between self-disclosure intensity and dyadic relationship quality were calculated for the gender, relationship, and gender-relationship pathways which yielded enough results to draw accurate comparisons. Both intensity-closeness and intensity-discord correlations were calculated for ten categories and are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2

Self-Disclosure Intensity vs. Closeness, Discord for Gender, Relationship, and Gender-Relationship Categories

Note. FF, $n = 20$; MM, $n = 15$; MF, $n = 9$; FM, $n = 7$; FRI, $n = 37$; RP, $n = 13$; FFFRI, $n = 18$; MMFRI, $n = 14$; MFRP, $n = 7$; FMRP, $n = 5$.

Some further analysis was conducted with correlations between intensity and relationship quality for gender pathways and relationship types. The FF and MM IC values were both significant and had moderately positive correlations, whereas any cross-gender IC values were weakly associated. The MM IC value was greater than the FF IC value, supporting the idea that when males engage in positive deviant behaviors like self-disclosure, they foster higher-quality relationships within a dyad. Additionally, the r -value for friends was greater than romantic partners and the r -value for same-sex dyads was greater than cross-sex dyads. Considering the high levels of closeness, this may be the result of romantic partners and cross-sex dyads developing relationship quality by means other than self-disclosure. Lastly, all-female dyads had positive correlations between intensity and discord while dyads with at least one male had negative correlations. Although females tend to have more turbulence within their relationships, individuals also tend to have more positive subjective experiences when disclosing to females as opposed to males.

Discussion

Existing literature has consistently observed that the social aspect of co-rumination, self-disclosure, suggests beneficial consequences for relationships during adolescence (Rose, 2021). This behavior occurs most frequently within dyads. Furthermore, adolescents tend to foster better quality relationships within and are more considerably influenced by dyads as opposed to peer groups. This study examined whether self-disclosure correlates to relationship quality for adolescents within dyads; the hypothesis that beneficial relationship quality would increase as self-disclosure intensity increased was supported. This research strengthens the understanding of the self-disclosure construct in existing literature and imparts additional, clarifying information on middle adolescents and dyads with relationships not limited to friendships. Nuanced findings may point to crucial circumstances and behaviors that benefit adolescents as they mature into adulthood.

Correlations

Because self-disclosure is more prevalent within dyads and adolescents tend to have better quality relationships in dyads, it was hypothesized that self-disclosure and dyadic relationship quality would be positively correlated. The study found a moderately positive correlation between these two constructs; the hypothesis was supported. This finding is likely due to implications akin to those of Piehler and Dishion (2007) and Chow et al. (2012) in that constructs like empathy and intimacy were consistent predictors of closeness and mutuality between friends. These two constructs are similar to self-disclosure since all address emotional aspects of an individual's life. Moreover, higher frequencies of behaviors that increased trust and satisfaction while decreasing relationship stress predicted greater relationship quality in adolescents; self-disclosure and beneficial relationship quality are related.

Further correlations were explored for differences in gender and dyadic relationship type. One notable observation was that in same-sex friendships, self-disclosure and dyadic relationship quality were more strongly correlated for males than females. This observation may be explained by the findings of Rose (2002), Chu (2005), and Piehler and Dishion (2007). These studies found that boys tend to engage in disruptive behaviors that are less hospitable to emotional disclosure and closer friendships and that non-normative behavior can have major beneficial impacts, respectively. Essentially, for boys, engaging in deviant behavior such as self-disclosure may result in social-emotional benefits. Since emotional disclosure is more prevalent among girls, as discussed by Rose (2021), behaviors like self-disclosure would not be considered deviant and would not yield an outcome as intense as self-disclosure between boys.

Another observation was that across all relationships, there was little to no correlation between self-disclosure and beneficial dyadic relationship quality for cross-sex dyads. This contrasted findings for same-sex dyads, of which had greater positive correlations. A possible explanation for this difference is that cross-sex dyads may develop closeness as a result of other means. For example, cross-sex dyads may simply spend quality time together or engage in similar behaviors to develop closeness instead of disclosing, as discussed by Laird et al. (1999).

A final correlational observation for relationships was that while self-disclosure and beneficial dyadic relationship quality were positively correlated for both friends and romantic partners, friends had a consistently greater correlation than romantic partners. This contrast could be due to similar reasons as the correlational disparities of same-sex and cross-sex dyads; romantic partners may develop closeness as a result of other means. An alternative conjecture is that self-disclosure may produce a more intense result in the absence of romantic feelings since disclosure may be more inherent to romantic relationships than to general friendships.

Correlations between self-disclosure and adverse dyadic relationship qualities were mixed. However, correlations for dyads with at least one male were consistently weakly negative, while correlations for all-female dyads were weakly positive. This was a surprising finding, but may be explained in part by Rose and Rudolph (2006) in that girls experience more relationship turbulence than boys. The negative correlation for dyads with at least one male is more difficult to explain, however, because Borowski and Rose (2021) found that adolescents have more positive subjective experiences when disclosing to girls as opposed to boys.

Point-scores

In conjunction with correlational observations, comparisons were made for beneficial and adverse dyadic relationship qualities, closeness and discord, between genders and dyadic relationship types. One observation was that across all relationships, intensity and closeness averages were consistently higher among dyads with female actors than male actors. This finding was expected; as discussed by Rose and Rudolph (2006) and Borowski and Rose (2021), females disclose more frequently and tend to have better quality relationships than males. This shows that females also tend to engage in relationship-oriented behaviors while males tend to engage in self-interested behaviors, supporting the findings of Chu (2005).

Another observation was that cross-sex dyads consistently scored higher for intensity and closeness than same-sex dyads. This could be due to females' greater openness to and engagement in self-disclosure compared to males, again as discussed by Rose and Rudolph (2006) and Borowski and Rose (2021). Increased openness and engagement may promote the emotional benefits of co-rumination and connect with relationship quality.

Next, it was observed that romantic partners mostly had higher intensity and closeness scores than friends. This is reasonable because generally, romantic dyads form a more intimate

bond than friends. As discussed by Piehler and Dishion (2007) and Chow et al. (2012), intimacy predicts closeness and trust in relationships.

Results for discord, or adverse dyadic relationship qualities, were mixed and did not yield any interpretable themes. However, discord scores were always lower than corresponding closeness scores. It can be assumed that in this population of adolescents, the majority of individuals have good-quality relationships.

Limitations

This study was not without its limitations. First, this study was time-constrained; a longitudinal study over numerous sequential months or years could not be performed. Gathering multiple data points over a period of time for each participant would make results more precise, and in conjunction with a qualitative aspect of the study - the absence of which is another limitation - would reveal possible directional effects for self-disclosure over time and more data that could point to causation and themes within conversations in dyads. A qualitative aspect, like open-ended questions about the nature of disclosure, was not included in the study because analyzing the complete data set would not be feasible in the allotted time to complete this study. Such an aspect may reveal motifs of self-disclosure that contribute to beneficial relationship quality more than other topics. Furthermore, extending the study to dyad partners would also unveil a wealth of information. Because this study focused only on dyad actors, responses were one-sided; partner responses would verify the actors' reports for each dyad as a whole. Next, this study relied on self-reported data. This is another limitation because participants may not have responded with complete honesty to the items. The participants may also have formed biases for the questions or answered based on biases. Finally, the study was limited by research fatigue and had to employ truncated instruments while gathering data. Because the instruments relied on

subscale averages and scores, reducing the number of items per subscale could have reduced the reliability of the instruments and produced inaccurate results.

Future Research

These limitations are all directions for future research. Specifically, longitudinal data and actor-partner data would be of utmost importance to model developmental effects for adolescents. Additionally, future studies could hone in on other age groups or demographics to bolster knowledge on self-disclosure and relationship quality for children and adults. Specifically, the disclosure and relationship quality of children affected by the COVID-19 pandemic, poverty, or war may differ to those of individuals with stable upbringings. The existing body of research may also benefit from studies regarding the differences in dyadic relationship qualities between boys and girls to address the disparity between these two genders.

Conclusion

Since adolescents face an increasing number of challenges - largely with respect to mental health - in the modern day, the correlation between self-disclosure intensity and dyadic relationship quality in a variety of relationships should be considered by initiatives and individuals during adolescence. For instance, this study highlights the utility of self-disclosure; adolescents may be more inclined to disclose, which would help individuals better understand their feelings and foster closer relationships. Gender and relationship differences should also be noted for their distinguishing characteristics for boys and girls. Because self-disclosure is prevalent and productive within dyads, adolescents who engage in disclosure with another individual are likely to develop beneficial characteristics as they mature into adulthood.

References

- Borowski, S. K., & Rose, A. J. (2021). Boys' and girls' interactions with same-gender friends and other-gender friends: A focus on problem disclosures. *Journal of Research on Adolescence*, 32(3), 1194–1209. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jora.12681>
- Calmes, C. A., & Roberts, J. E. (2008). Rumination in interpersonal relationships: Does co-rumination explain gender differences in emotional distress and relationship satisfaction among college students? *Cognitive Therapy and Research*, 32(4), 577–590. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10608-008-9200-3>
- Chow, C. M., Ruhl, H., & Buhrmester, D. (2012). The mediating role of interpersonal competence between adolescents' empathy and friendship quality: A dyadic approach. *Journal of Adolescence*, 36(1), 191–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.adolescence.2012.10.004>
- Chow, C. M., & Tan, C. C. (2013). Attachment and commitment in dyadic friendships: Mediating roles of satisfaction, quality of alternatives, and investment size. *Journal of Relationships Research*, 4. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jrr.2013.4>
- Chu, J. Y. (2005). Adolescent boys' friendships and peer group Culture. *New Directions for Child and Adolescent Development*, 2005(107), 7–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cd.118>
- Cillessen, A. H., Jiang, X. L., West, T. V., & Laszkowski, D. K. (2005). Predictors of dyadic friendship quality in adolescence. *International Journal of Behavioral Development*, 29(2), 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01650250444000360>
- Furman, W., & Buhrmester, D. (1985). Children's perceptions of the personal relationships in their social networks. *Developmental Psychology*, 21(6), 1016–1024. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0012-1649.21.6.1016>

- Harris, J. R. (1995). Where is the child's environment? A group socialization theory of development. *Psychological Review*, *102*(3), 458–489.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295x.102.3.458>
- Laird, R. D., Pettit, G. S., Dodge, K. A., & Bates, J. E. (1999). Best friendships, group relationships, and antisocial behavior in early adolescence. *The Journal of Early Adolescence*, *19*(4), 413–437. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0272431699019004001>
- Legerski, J., Biggs, B. K., Greenhoot, A. F., & Sampilo, M. L. (2014). Emotion talk and friend responses among early adolescent same-sex friend Dyads. *Social Development*, *24*(1), 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.1111/sode.12079>
- Piehler, T. F., & Dishion, T. J. (2007). Interpersonal Dynamics within adolescent friendships: Dyadic mutuality, deviant talk, and patterns of antisocial behavior. *Child Development*, *78*(5), 1611–1624. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2007.01086.x>
- Rose, A. J. (2002). Co-rumination in the friendships of girls and boys. *Child Development*, *73*(6), 1830–1843. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8624.00509>
- Rose, A. J., & Rudolph, K. D. (2006). A review of sex differences in peer relationship processes: Potential trade-offs for the emotional and behavioral development of girls and boys. *Psychological Bulletin*, *132*(1), 98–131. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.132.1.98>
- Rose, A. J., Schwartz-Mette, R. A., Smith, R. L., Asher, S. R., Swenson, L. P., Carlson, W., & Waller, E. M. (2012). How girls and boys expect disclosure about problems will make them feel: Implications for friendships. *Child Development*, *83*(3), 844–863.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8624.2012.01734.x>
- Rose, A. J. (2021). The costs and benefits of co-rumination. *Child Development Perspectives*, *15*(3), 176–181. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdep.12419>

Smetana, J. G., Campione-Barr, N., & Metzger, A. (2006). Adolescent development in interpersonal and societal contexts. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 57(1), 255–284.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.57.102904.190124>

Snell, W. E., Miller, R. S., & Belk, S. S. (1988). Development of the emotional self-disclosure scale. *Sex Roles*, 18(1–2), 59–73. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf00288017>

Appendix A

Emotional Self-Disclosure Scale Content Area Item Examples

(1) Depression, “How often have you discussed times when you felt discouraged?”; (2) Happiness, “How often have you discussed times when you felt cheerful?”; (3) Jealousy, “How often have you discussed times when you felt envious?”; (4) Anxiety, “How often have you discussed times when you felt troubled?”; (5) Anger, “How often have you discussed times when you felt enraged?”; (6) Calmness, “How often have you discussed times when you felt relaxed?”; (7) Apathy, “How often have you discussed times when you felt detached?”; and (8) Fear, “How often have you discussed times when you felt afraid?”.

Appendix B

Network of Relationships Inventory-Relationship Qualities Version Subscale Item

Examples

(1) Companionship, “How often do you and this person go places and do things together?”; (2) Intimate disclosure, “How often do you share secrets and private feelings with this person?”; (3) Pressure, “How often does this person try to get you to do things that you don’t like?”; (4) Satisfaction, “How much do you like the way things are between you and this person?”; (5) Conflict, “How often do you and this person get mad at or get in fights with each other?”; (6) Emotional support, “How often do you depend on this person to cheer things up when you are feeling down or upset?”; (7) Criticism, “How often does this person say mean or harsh things to you?”; (8) Approval, “How often does this person seem really proud of you?”; (9) Dominance, “How often does this person get their way when you two do not agree about what to do?”; and (10) Exclusion, “How often does this person not include you in activities?”.

Appendix C

Self-Disclosure and Dyadic Relationship Quality Questionnaire (begins on following page)

Self-Disclosure and Dyadic Relationship Quality Questionnaire

The purpose of this study is to explore the correlation between self-disclosure and dyadic relationship quality. The questionnaire contains 40 questions and should take no longer than 10 minutes, and there are minimal to no risks involved. Your participation is completely voluntary and there will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate. You may stop participating at any time and you may choose not to answer any specific question. Your answers are completely anonymous; no identifying data will be collected.

If you have any questions about this study, contact the researcher, [REDACTED] or the AP Capstone Research teacher, [REDACTED], at [REDACTED].

* Indicates required question

1. Check here to indicate you have read the information above and consent to participate in this study. *

Mark only one oval.

I consent to participate in this study.

Preliminary Information

2. Which grade level are you currently in?

Mark only one oval.

9th

10th

11th

12th

3. Which gender do you most strongly identify with?

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

Think of someone around your age who you know personally and feel close to or connected with in some way.

4. What is your relationship with this person?

Mark only one oval.

- Classmate
- Counselor
- Friend/best friend
- Romantic partner
- Other: _____

5. Which gender does this person most strongly identify with?

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

Questions

With this person in mind, please answer the following questions as accurately as possible using the scale provided:

- 1 = Never or hardly at all
- 2 = Seldom or not too much
- 3 = Sometimes or somewhat
- 4 = Often or very much
- 5 = Always or extremely much

6. How often have you discussed times when you felt depressed?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

7. How often have you discussed times when you felt anxious?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

8. How often have you discussed times when you felt calm?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

9. How often have you discussed times when you felt apathetic?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

10. How often have you discussed times when you felt afraid?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

11. How often have you discussed times when you felt discouraged?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

12. How often have you discussed times when you felt cheerful?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

13. How often have you discussed times when you felt troubled?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

14. How often have you discussed times when you felt envious?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

15. How often have you discussed times when you felt irritated?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

16. How often have you discussed times when you felt suspicious?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

17. How often have you discussed times when you felt pleased?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

18. How often have you discussed times when you felt enraged?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

19. How often have you discussed times when you felt relaxed?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

20. How often have you discussed times when you felt detached?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

21. How often have you discussed times when you felt alarmed?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

Questions (continued)

22. How often do you spend fun time with this person?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

23. How often do you turn to this person for support with personal problems?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

24. How often does this person get their way when you two do not agree about what to do?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

25. How often does this person not include you in activities?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

26. How often do you and this person go places and do things together?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

27. How often do you tell this person everything that you are going through?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

28. How often does this person try to get you to do things that you don't like?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

29. How often do you and this person get mad at or get in fights with each other?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

30. How often does this person criticize you?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

31. How often does this person seem really proud of you?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

32. How often does this person end up being the one who makes the decisions for both of you?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

33. How often does it seem like this person ignores you?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

34. How often do you share secrets and private feelings with this person?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

35. How often does this person pressure you to do the things that he or she wants?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

36. How often do you and this person argue with each other?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

37. How often do you depend on this person to cheer things up when you are feeling down or upset?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

38. How often does this person say mean or harsh things to you?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

39. How much do you like the way things are between you and this person?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

40. How much does this person like or approve of the things you do?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

41. How satisfied are you with your relationship with this person?

Mark only one oval.

Never or hardly at all

1

2

3

4

5

Always or extremely much

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